

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Media Kit for WISH-OI

Deliverable D12.2

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<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

About this document

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Review:

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History of changes

Version	Date	Description	Authors (A) & Reviewers (R)
1	26 April 2024	First version delivered to the European Commission.	As listed on the second page.
2	29 September 2024	Revision after the 1st EC review, comments of the reviewers have been addressed. Delivery to the European Commission.	A: Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), Chiara Bearzotti R: British Antarctic Survey (UKRI-BAS): Ruta Hamilton

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1. Publishable summary

The present media kit lives fully online as a series of static, downloadable resources. It has been drafted to announce the inclusion of NASC as a partner in the OCEAN:ICE consortium and to update the dissemination materials used by OCEAN:ICE so far. NASC was added to the consortium with a proposal under the call HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-06-01. The original proposal was called WISH-OI. After the grant agreement preparation phase, the contents of the WISH-OI approved proposal have been integrated fully in the OCEAN:ICE work plan. For this reason, the original acronym, WISH-OI, is no longer used.

2. Work performed and main achievements

This media kit includes the following elements:

- One or more narratives
- Testimonials
- A bio or About Us text on NASC
- Social media channels for tagging
- Insights on the planned research activities
- High-quality brand identity images (logos and other images)
- Updated promotional materials for the project

Narratives

The narrative elaborated with NASC evolves along the following texts (examples).

Text 1: The perspective of OCEAN:ICE

OCEAN:ICE is delighted to welcome a new partner to OCEAN:ICE this month. The National Antarctic Science Center of Ukraine (NASC) joins OCEAN:ICE and helps to make us a truly circum-Antarctic project. Under the widening access programme of Horizon Europe, NASC has joined as full partner and will contribute both fieldwork and deployment of ocean floats as well as meteorological observations and analysis of extreme events around the peninsula. The key task of NASC is, using the logistical support of its research vessel 'Noosfera', to build a bridge between practical measurements in the ocean, using ocean floats, and theoretical modelling, such as state-of-the-art particle tracking model, under ice shelves. Some of you may already know our new colleagues via other Horizon Europe projects that NASC also participates in, but we hope to profile the NASC team in next month's newsletter and welcome them in person to the annual project meeting in Copenhagen, 23-25 September 2024.

The funding comes from Horizon Europe programme, from the call [HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-06-01](#)

Text 2: The perspective of NASC**UKRAINE JOINED AN IMPORTANT INTERNATIONAL STUDY OF THE ANTARCTIC ICE**

Great news: the National Antarctic Science Center (NASC) joined the OCEAN:ICE project on 1st April 2024. OCEAN:ICE stands for “Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System” is a large Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission. The consortium also includes UK partners which are funded by the UK Research and Innovation.

This project is aimed to assess the impacts of key Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean processes on Planet Earth, via their influence on sea level rise, deep water formation, ocean circulation and climate. The loss of ice from Antarctica is enormously important for our sea level rise, and most of the loss of ice from the continent happens at the ocean-ice sheet interface, driven by warm ocean currents, so this is why OCEAN:ICE is focusing on the processes that are driving that melting.

Initially, the project was implemented by a consortium of 17 partners, led by Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI). In September 2023, DMI and NASC applied for and have been granted additional funding under the Horizon Europe programme to welcome NASC as a new partner in the project.

What will be NASC contribution to this paramount project?

- NASC will fill in some of the remaining “data gaps” around Antarctica by deploying an additional set of innovative equipment - profiling floats in the Southern Ocean. A float is an oceanographic instrument platform used for making subsurface measurements in the ocean without the need for a vessel, propeller, or a person operating it. Floats measure the physical and chemical parameters of the ocean in detail, such as measuring the direction and water velocity or the temperature and salinity. These measures will help to understand better the seasonal exchanges between cold Weddell Sea waters and relatively warmer central West Antarctic Peninsula waters.
- In addition, NASC will examine the impact of precipitation on the ice shelf mass budget by snowfall and rain using high-resolution regional atmospheric modelling.

In addition, the additional funding will help develop collaborations between scientists in Ukraine and internationally as well as leverage expertise in OCEAN:ICE to develop existing NASC capabilities and new observational and analytical skill sets and extend them to applications with the Ukrainian research vessel “Noosfera”.

The project will run until 31st October 2026, and the budget allocated for NASC is .000 Euro. Read more about the project at <https://ocean-ice.eu/>

Testimonials' quotes

Evgen Dykyi, the director of NASC: *'Now humanity faces a difficult time: when some act to solve global problems such as climate change and relevant sea level rise, others call us back to dark times full of wars, violence and authoritarianism. Ukraine is now on the front line of this battle of visions for the future. So even in these hard times for us it is really important to contribute to the world science and solution of global problems and we are happy to have this new opportunity to cooperate, share and investigate together within OCEAN:ICE'.*

Ruth Mottram, OCEAN:ICE project coordinator, senior scientist at the Danish Meteorological Institute mentioned: *"NASC will enhance the existing OCEAN:ICE project by adding new observations and analysis as well as innovative numerical modelling to ocean and atmospheric processes and regions not presently represented in the project. NASC logistical support will expand existing OCEAN:ICE observations to areas not covered by OCEAN:ICE around Antarctica, allowing us to close the gap and become a truly circum-polar project".*

A bio or About Us text: NASC

NASC is the Ukrainian National Antarctic Scientific Center. The Center is the main organization for conducting research expeditions in Antarctica, coordinating of scientific research, selecting and training

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winterers, and ensuring the vital functions of the Ukrainian Antarctic "Akademik Vernadsky" station.

According to the Decree of the President of Ukraine dated December 15, 1999, the Center was subordinated to the Ministry of Education and Science. Taking into account

the national and international importance of comprehensive scientific research in Antarctica, the institution was granted status of a national scientific center by the Decree of the President of Ukraine of December 23, 2004.

Thanks to the active efforts of the Center, in the same year Ukraine received the status of a Consultative Party to the Antarctic Treaty, which gives the state the right to vote for any decision to be taken in a consensual manner concerning all aspects of the organization of human activity in Antarctica and the further development of the international legal regime of the region.

To date, the Center has organized and provided [27 Ukrainian Antarctic expeditions](#) and continuous work and research at the station "Academician Vernadsky".

The National Antarctic Scientific Center of Ukraine cooperates with several authoritative domestic research institutes and dozens of foreign partners, and supports Ukraine's participation in international organizations involved in the study and preservation of the "ice" continent and the Southern Ocean.

More: <http://uac.gov.ua/en/about-en/nasc-history/>

Social media channels

The following accounts on Social Media will be tagged in the planned social media plans to be launched from the OCEAN:ICE channels.

Social media OCEAN:ICE

- [@OCEANICE_EU](#)
- <https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>
- <https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

Social media of NASC

- https://twitter.com/nasc_ua
- <https://www.facebook.com/AntarcticCenter/>

Social media of the Danish Meteorological Institute

- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/dmi/mycompany/>
- <https://twitter.com/dmidk>
- <https://www.facebook.com/danmarkvejret/>

Social media European Commission, DG RTD and relevant the EC research agency (REA)

- [@EUScienceInnov](#)
- [@REA_research](#)
- [@EU_Commission](#)
- [@HorizonEU](#)
- [#EURResearchArea #HorizonEU](#)
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-commission/mycompany/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/european-commission-joint-research-centre/>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ncpwideranet/>

Insights on the planned research activities together with NASC

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instrument platform used for making subsurface measurements in the ocean without the need for a vessel, propeller, or a person operating it. Floats measure the physical and chemical parameters of the ocean in detail, such as measuring the direction and water velocity or the temperature and salinity. These measures will help to understand better the seasonal exchanges between cold Weddell Sea waters and relatively warmer central West Antarctic Peninsula waters.

- In addition, NASC will examine the impact of precipitation on ice shelf mass budget by snowfall and rain using high-resolution regional atmospheric modelling.

High-quality brand identity images (logos and other images)

The following graphics have been updated and will be used to promote the widening of the consortium on the website and on social media.

Banner for the widening of the OCEAN:ICE consortium

Pert chart

Updated consortium logos

Promotional materials for the project

The following materials have been updated and will be uploaded to the project website and to Zenodo in the next days:

- 1) Updated OCEAN:ICE poster.
- 2) Updated factsheets for Cordis and for the EU Polar Cluster.
- 3) Updated pitch deck and graphics.

3. Impact

This deliverable is instrumental to the achievement of all the objectives of the project as described in the description of the action, but it is more closely linked to the achievement of O7-O11, where NASC will be directly involved.

- O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.
- O8: Develop and enhance the technical skills of Ukrainian research and technical staff, strengthening competencies in deployment, analysis, dissemination, exploitation and research management.
- O9: Fill in the existing “hole” in the quasi-circumpolar OCEAN-ICE analysis of shelf transport and exchange with the contribution of Ukrainian purchased and deployed profiling floats.
- O10: Resolve the structure and temporal evolution of the seasonal exchanges between cold Weddell Sea waters and relatively warmer central West Antarctic Peninsula waters.
- O11: Examine the impact of precipitation on ice shelf mass budget by snowfall and rain using high-resolution regional atmospheric modelling.